

The effect of interface properties on the mechanical behavior of 3D braided composites under unidirectional tensile loading

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SUMMARY

Interfacial damage mechanism is considered by cohesive zone model in finite element analysis of a representative volume cell (RVC) of 3D four-directional braided composites. A parametrical study is carried out to evaluate the influence of interfacial properties on the stress-strain curve and corresponding failure modes.

Keywords: 3D braided, composites, interface, cohesive zone model, damage

ARTICLE OUTLINE

The mechanical behaviour of 3D (three dimension) four-directional braided composites subjected to unidirectional tensile loading is studied by computational micromechanics. The main failure mechanisms of the braided composites are observed in experiment. In addition, a representative volume cell (RVC) with interface layer is modelled. The stress-strain curves are obtained by finite element method with cohesive zone model. Meanwhile, a parametrical study is conducted to assess the influence of interfacial properties on the mechanical properties of the braided composites.

Experiment Analysis and Modelling

The unidirectional tensile experiment of 3D four-directional braided composites is applied to observe the macroscopic failure modes as shown in Fig.1. Several yarns pull-out are found in the fracture surface. In addition, some proxy matrix cracks are appeared in the specimen surface.

In order to study the influence of interface properties, a representative volume cell (RVC) which includes the yarns (an assembly of fibers)/yarns and yarns/matrix interfaces is established by finite element model as shown in Fig. 2. The interface law is constructed by cohesive zone model. In addition, the progressive damage model of yarns and matrix utilized in Ref. [3] is adopted in the simulation.

Numerical Results and Discussion

The influence of the interfacial strength on the unidirectional tensile mechanical behaviours for the braided composites whose interfacial strength varied from $c/3$ to $5c/3$ ($c=60\text{MPa}$) is plotted in Fig. 3. The initial stiffness is not affected by the interface strength, but the stress-strain curve of the composites with low interfacial strength departs early from initial linear due to interface debonding. When the interface

debonding is approached some extent, the stress-strain curve becomes linear again. The tangential moduli of the initial and second linear of the stress-strain curve are not affected by interfacial strength as shown Fig. 3. Meanwhile, it is found from Fig.3 that the decohesive areas are mainly distributed in the yarn/yarn interfaces and the yarn/matrix interfaces whose normal directions have angles near 45° with the tensile direction. When the interface fracture energy is varied from small to large, the magnitude of the interface fracture energy is almost not affected the variation of stress-strain curve.

Fig. 1 Tensile fracture photographs of specimen of the braided composites.

Fig.2 (a) a RVC of the braided composites;(b) interface phase

Fig. 3 The influence of interface strength on the stress-strain curve of the braided composites and interfacial damage state at the circle point in curve.

References

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